

Agrarian Problems and Farmer Suicide in India ‘A Spatio Temporal Analysis’

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: May

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3402652>

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Abstract

The main objective of the study is to know the death of the farmers caused by the suicide through space and time. A simple methodology is followed by collecting secondary data mainly from NCRB of India and primary data through simple questionnaire to know the reasons for the suicide of the farmers. Geography plays a dominant role in the field of agriculture. The geographical factors like soil, temperature, rainfall irrigation are the controlling factors. The rainfall monsoon decides Indian agriculture as more than 60% of the Indian agriculture is rain fed. If the monsoon fails the farmers will be in pressure and burden which leads to their suicide.

Keywords: Farmer, Suicide, State, District.

Agrarian Problems and Farmer Suicide in India ‘A Spatio Temporal Analysis’

Now a day's the farmer's suicide is common news in all the media. The main objective of the study is to know the death of the farmers caused by the suicide through space and time. A simple methodology is followed by collecting secondary data mainly from NCRB of India and primary data through simple questionnaire to know the reasons for the suicide of the farmers. The collected data has been represented in the form of table, graphs and maps.

Farmer is one who entirely depends on the land and earns their lively hood by tilling the land. This process is entirely controlled by the geographic factors like soil, rainfall, temperature etc. when these factors lack its immediate effects on the agriculture later in turn on the farmer. India is an agrarian country with around 70% of its people directly or indirectly depending on agriculture. The farmer's suicides in India are directly connected with their economic status. We say the farmers are the back bone of the economy, in India most of the farmers are economically in weaker section. For all kinds of their agricultural activates they mainly depends on money which they borrow either from the governmental sectors or from the private money lenders. When they fail to return the money due failure of agriculture pressure on them increases leads to health issues and family problems which in turn leads to commit suicide. It accounts for 11.2% of all suicide in India.

National Crime Records Bureau, an office of the Ministry of Home Affairs Government of India, has been collecting and publishing suicide statistics for India since the 1950s, as annual Accidental Deaths & Suicides in India reports. It started separately collecting and publishing farmer's suicide statistics from 1995.

Brief Review

Ganapathi and Venkoba Rao analyzed suicides in parts of Tamil Nadu in 1966. They recommended that the distribution of agricultural organo-phosphorus compounds be restricted. Similarly, Nandi et al. in 1979 noted the role of freely available agricultural insecticides in suicides in rural West Bengal and suggested that their availability be regulated. Hegde studied rural suicides in villages of northern Karnataka over 1962 to 1970, and stated the suicide incidence rate to be 5.7 per 100,000 populations. Reddy, in 1993, reviewed high rates of farmer suicides in Andhra Pradesh and its relationship to farm size and productivity. Reporting in popular press about farmers' suicides in India began in the mid-1990s, particularly by Palagummi Sainath. In the 2000s, the issue gained international attention and a variety of Indian government initiatives.

Temporal Analysis: National Crime Records Bureau which works under Ministry of Home Affairs Government of India is collecting and publishing data related to farmer's suicide since 1995. In 2014, the NCRB of India reported 5,650 farmer suicides. The highest number of farmer suicides was recorded in 2004 when 18,241 farmers committed suicide. The farmer's suicide rate in India has ranged between 1.4 and 1.8 per 100,000 total populations, over a 10-year period through 2005.

Year	Total farmer suicide	Year	Total farmer suicide
1995	10,720	2005	17,131
1996	13,729	2006	17,060
1997	13,622	2007	16,632
1998	16,015	2008	16,796
1999	16,082	2009	17,368
2000	16,603	2010	15,964
2001	16,415	2011	14,027
2002	17,971	2012	13,754
2003	17,164	2013	11,772
2004	18,241	2014	12,360
	Source: NCRB	2015	12,602

Spatial Analysis

The farmers of the southern states are committing more suicides rather than the north Indian. The most common cause for suicide in South India is a combination of social issues, such as interpersonal and family problems, financial difficulties, and pre-existing mental illness. Suicidal ideation is as culturally accepted in south India as in some high-income countries. The high suicide rates in southern states of India may be because of social acceptance of suicide as a method to deal with difficulties. As per the data obtained by the NCRB of India, Maharashtra stands first both in the suicide of the farmers and farmer's labourer, and Punjab stands at the last, followed by Karnataka, Telangana, Madhya Pradesh and Chattisgarh. The reason could be the effects of Monsoon in those states as most of the parts of those states are practicing rain fed agriculture, whereas Punjab is highly irrigated by the perennial rivers Indus and its system.

States	Farmer's Suicide		Farmer Labour suicide	
	2015	2016	2015	2016
Maharashtra	2550	3030	1111	1261
Karnataka	1212	1197	867	372
Telangana	632	1358	0	0
Madhya Pradesh	599	581	722	709
Chattisgarh	585	854	0	0
Andhra Pradesh	239	516	565	400
Punjab	222	100	0	0

Reasons

Several reasons could be attributed to the farmer's suicides. The main reasons are shown in the following table. The failure of crops is the main reason which could be attributed to Monsoon which either leads to flood or drought. Most of the farmers who commit suicides are the small and marginal farmers of rain fed agriculture.

Reasons	% of Suicide
Failure of crops	16.84
Other Reasons Debt Chit funds	17.69
Family Problems	13.27
Disease	09.73

Marriages mainly daughters	5.31
Political affiliation	4.42
Property disputes	2.65
Price crash	2.65
House construction and house furnish	2.65
Loss from bad habits and non farming activity	1.77
Failure of Bore Wells	0.88

Farmer Suicides in Karnataka

In Karnataka also the vagaries of monsoon is the key factor for the farmer's suicide. The number of deaths is highest in 2015-16 where as it is very least in 2011-12 and 2013-14.

Year	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16
No. of cases	205	114	94	176	182	139	145	117	58	77	58	48	284

The above map depicts northern Karnataka records highest death than the southern parts. In the first category Mandya records highest of 56 followed by Haveri 44, Tumukur 36 and Mysuru 33, Raichur Belagavi, Gadag, Davanagere, Chikamagaluru and Hassan ranging between 20 and 30 are in the second category. Bangalore urban records least with one, Uttarakannada, Udpi, and Dhakshinakannada, Koagu and Chamarajanagara districts, single digit figures have reported.

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